

EVALUATION OF BOND TEST METHODS FOR GFRP RODS GLUED IN GLULAM

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ABSTRACT

Despite considerable studies in glued-in rods, there are no established design formulas in Eurocode 5. Variations in test methods can result in contradictory experimental findings hindering standardisation. This study aims to compare two commonly applied bond test methods, the ‘pull-pull’ and the ‘pull-compression’ tests for Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) rods glued in timber. Finite Element (FE) studies are compared with Digital Image Correlation (DIC) analyses and parametric FE analyses are conducted based on the contact stiffness to fit experimental and numerical findings. Results suggest that when the numerical contact stiffness is up to ten times higher than the experimental values, good agreement between the experimental and numerical pull-out load versus slip is attained. Displacement fields from the FE models are shown to be in qualitative agreement with those obtained by DIC.

KEYWORDS

GFRP rods, Glued-in rods, Timber, Bond test methods

INTRODUCTION

Glued-in rods (GiRs) are a type of timber connection that exhibit higher stiffness and axial load transition capacity at short embedment lengths compared with widely used timber connections with mechanical fasteners. They are also preferred in rehabilitation of historical timber buildings where timber decay can take place by removing the original biodegraded section and attaching a new wood section via glued-in rods in internal holes or external grooves to achieve moment continuity (Schober et al., 2015).

Steel rods are most commonly applied in GiRs due to their desired ductility performance. The use of composite materials such as carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) and glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) has been proposed for enhanced durability performance, lower weight and better chemical compatibility between the resin and the FRP rods (Madhoushi & Ansell, 2004). To induce a pseudo-ductile performance in glued-in FRP rods in timber, a wedge-type anchoring profile in the timber hole penetration has been experimentally investigated by Toumpanaki & Ramage (2021) for short bonded lengths. FRP rods are also promising for retrofitting timber structures due to their lightweight nature (e.g. near surface-mounted systems).

The current version of Eurocode 5 does not provide any guidance regarding the design of glued-in rods. A proposal for a design methodology for GiRs was implemented in 1997 in a preliminary version of Eurocode 5 Part 2 (2003), but was disregarded by the CEN/TC/250/SC5 committee in 2003 (Stepinac et al., 2013). Various design formulae have been proposed by researchers and national design guidelines to evaluate the axial withdrawal capacity of steel rods glued in timber incorporating a range of differing variables such as the effect of timber density (Riberholt, 1988) or edge distances (NZTDS, 2007). Variations among studies may lie in the lack of a standardised test method to evaluate the axial withdrawal capacity of GiRs and inherent variability among materials (e.g. timber density and type of adhesive). The recently published BS EN 17334:2021 (BSI, 2021) provides a more unified design guidance for glued-in rod connections ranging from universal testing to manufacturing and design rules (Annex A). The second generation of Eurocode 5 (2022) to be released in 2025 will include design guidelines for glued-in rods defined as bonded-in rods addressing some of the existing design gaps for practitioners.

The most common test method employed in literature to assess the axial withdrawal capacity of GiRs is the ‘pull-pull’ test method (Figure 1a) where rods are glued in both ends of a timber element and pulled apart in a tensile test. The ‘pull-compression’ test method (Figure 1b) is similar to the pull-out bond test method of steel reinforcing bars in concrete cubes and has also been adopted for GiRs due to its simplicity and ease of application for mechanical screening. In this test methodology the rods are pulled out from a timber specimen that reacts against a fixed steel plate. Deviations in the axial withdrawal capacity of GiRs have been investigated experimentally (Toumpanaki & Ramage, 2022) and numerically (Gustafsson & Serrano, 2002) based on these two test methods. A 63% difference in the bond strength of GFRP rods glued in glulam with a bonded length of 50 mm has been experimentally reported between the ‘pull-compression’ (Toumpanaki & Ramage, 2021) and ‘pull-pull’ (Toumpanaki & Ramage, 2022) test methods, with the latter yielding higher strengths. In the aforementioned studies, the ‘pull-compression’ test method exhibited a 82% higher secant stiffness at the serviceability limit state (SLS). This was attributed to the compressive stresses developed at the loaded end pressing against the reaction plate. This is in contrast with the testing of steel bars in reinforced concrete where the ‘pull-compression’ test method yields higher bond strengths, which is attributed to the compressive stresses having a constraining effect that counteracts the bearing stresses during pull-out (Tastani & Pantazopoulou, 2002). The anisotropic nature of timber and its lower tensile and shear strengths and elastic moduli compared with concrete should also be taken into account when analysing the differences in bond strengths obtained by different test methods applied to these materials.

Figure 1: Bond test methods for the axial withdrawal capacity of Glued-in Rods (GiRs).

The Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique is a contact-free method that allows visualisation of surface strain fields in loaded structural elements revealing any strain concentrations taking place during testing. DIC has been adopted in wood testing at different length scales, from measurement of fibre deformation in black spruce latewood (Laurence & Groom, 1996) to the estimation of local accelerations in timber buildings during shake table testing (Sieffert et al., 2016). In DIC a digital image is subdivided into subsets of given size and with characteristic pixel intensity values. A subset in the reference image (Figure 2a) is compared against neighbouring subsets in the deformed image (Figure 2b) and the best match is selected based on either cross-correlation (CC) or sum of squared differences (SSD) criteria. To account for high strain and rotation effects within the deformed subset, higher order shape functions may be introduced in the tracking process which allow the subset to deform and thus increasing the correlation between reference and deformed images. The displacement

field in the deformed image is defined based on the differences between the x and y coordinates of the subset centroids in consecutive images. The strain field is derived by differentiating the displacement values. The accuracy of DIC can be affected by many factors such as the subset size, image texture, sub-pixel optimisation algorithm, image noise, out-of plane distortion, camera self-heating and lens distortion. The effects of those factors on the accuracy of displacement measurements has been investigated by many authors (e.g. Pan et al., 2008).

Digital Image Correlation techniques have been adopted in Biscaia et al. (2021) to derive bond stress-slip models in externally bonded CFRP systems in timber. The authors used strain gauge readings along the bonded length to validate DIC measurements and check the accuracy of DIC for slip readings. The mean absolute slip deviation values between the DIC method and strain gauge data increased with increasing load with a maximum deviation of 0.32 mm being recorded. This was attributed to the predefined time intervals and facet size between consecutive snapshots that failed to accurately capture large deformations at failure. Furthermore, the authors found that the accuracy of the DIC method was compromised after debonding at the post-failure range.

Figure 2: Digital Image Correlation (DIC) principles.

The present study aims to compare two commonly used bond test methods, the ‘pull-pull’ and the ‘pull-compression’ tests, for Glass FRP rods glued in glulam. The strain fields as derived from DIC are compared with FE data. This study sheds light on the observed deviations between the two test methods when applied to timber particularly due to the anisotropic nature of the material.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Materials and specimen preparation

Sand coated and helically wrapped GFRP rods (Figure 3) of nominal diameter $D = 10$ mm were glued in glulam (GL24h) with a two-part thixotropic epoxy adhesive (Sikadur 30). Detailed material properties can be found in Toumpanaki et al. (2021) and are summarised in Table 1. Two specimen geometries were adopted depending on the bond test method employed (‘pull-compression’ or ‘pull-pull’ tests). In both test methods the bonded length was 50 mm ($5D$) and the specimen cross-section was constant at 70 mm \times 70 mm, complying with previous test recommendations (Aicher et al. 1998). The glue-line thickness was 3.0 mm in ‘pull-pull’ tests and 1.5 mm in ‘pull-compression’ tests. The specimens were cut close to the bondline with a table saw and sanded before a speckle pattern was applied on the surface of interest.

Figure 3: GFRP rod.

Experimental methodology

Both the ‘pull-compression’ and ‘pull-pull’ tests were conducted in an Instron machine of 150 kN load capacity under displacement control with a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. High resolution photos (4512×3000 pixels for the ‘pull-compression’ and 6016×4000 pixels for the ‘pull-pull’ test method) were taken with a Nikon D3200 digital camera and a remote control at regular time intervals (every 10 s). The camera was placed at a distance of 300-370 mm from the specimen depending on the test repetition. A LED panel illuminated the specimen to eliminate any shadow effects. Before every test, photos of a checkerboard were taken to calibrate the camera using the camera calibrator application in Matlab (Mathworks, 2022). All images were corrected for lens distortion in Matlab before processing their sequence with the image analysis tool Ncorr (Blaber et al., 2015).

FINITE ELEMENT METHODOLOGY

The ‘pull-pull’ and ‘pull-compression’ tests were modelled in the FEA package Abaqus/Standard (2018). The numerical models and respective test set ups for both specimens are depicted in Figure 4. The epoxy, GFRP rod and glulam were modelled with eight-node continuum elements with reduced integration (C3D8R). The epoxy adhesive was modelled as a linear-elastic isotropic material, the GFRP rod as transversely isotropic and the glulam as an orthotropic material. The contact between the GFRP rod and the epoxy adhesive was modelled with tie constraints since interface shear failure was not observed in the rod/resin interface. The contact at the wood/resin interface was modelled with a surface-to-surface interaction. The same contact properties were adopted at the end of the bonded length between the timber face and the epoxy and rod face in the ‘pull-pull’ test specimen. The reaction plate in the ‘pull-compression’ test specimen was modelled with rigid elements (R3D4). The contact between the reaction plate and the timber face was modelled using a ‘hard contact’ interaction in the normal direction and a frictional penalty method in the tangential direction with a Coulomb friction coefficient of 0.3. The epoxy thickness in the ‘pull-pull’ and ‘pull-compression’ test specimens were 3.0 mm and 1.5 mm respectively to compare with the actual geometry of the experiments. The load was applied via displacement-control of the end of the GFRP rod. The nodes at the bottom face of the ‘pull-pull’ model were ‘pinned’ since only the upper half of the specimen was modelled, and in the experiments a steel rod with a thicker glueline was used in the bottom half of the specimen to prevent failure there. In the ‘pull-compression’ model the rigid plate was restrained in all translational directions. The material properties and contact interaction properties of the FE models are summarised in Tables 1 and 2 correspondingly.

FE parametric studies were conducted in order to fit the numerical pull-out load versus loaded end slip response with the experimental findings. The variables were the contact stiffness K_{nn} , $K_{tt,1}$ and $K_{tt,2}$ which varied from the baseline experimental values to one and two orders of magnitude greater values, as shown in Table 2.

a) Pull-pull test specimen.

b) Pull-compression test specimen.

Figure 4: Finite Element models and test set ups.

Table 1: Material properties of the FEA modelling.

Material	E_1 (MPa)	E_2 (MPa)	E_3 (MPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	G_{12} (MPa)	G_{13} (MPa)	G_{23} (MPa)
Spruce	11,600 ^[3]	580 ^[3]	928 ^[3]	0.04 ^[3]	0.04 ^[3]	0.27 ^[3]	880 ^[3]	830 ^[3]	88 ^[3]
GFRP	46,000 ^[1]	9,100 ^[2]	9,100 ^[2]	0.05 ^[2]	0.05 ^[2]	0.25 ^[2]	14,000 ^[2]	14,000 ^[2]	1,300 ^[2]
Epoxy	11,200 ^[1]	11,200 ^[1]	11,200 ^[1]	0.3 ^[1]	0.3 ^[1]	0.3 ^[1]	4,308 ^[1]	4,308 ^[1]	4,308 ^[1]

Sources: ^[1] nominal values as provided by the manufacturer; ^[2] engineering constants from Madhoushi & Ansell (2017); ^[3] engineering constants for GL24h from (Wood Handbook, 2010).

Table 2: Contact interaction properties of the FEA modelling.

Interface	σ_{33} (MPa)	τ_{13} (MPa)	τ_{23} (MPa)	K_{nn} (MPa/mm)	$K_{tt,1}$ (MPa/mm)	$K_{tt,2}$ (MPa/mm)	G_f (MPa mm)
Wood/Resin, 'pull-pull'	5 ^[1]	9.7 ^[2]	9.7 ^[2]	39.9 ^[4]	15.4 ^[2]	15.4 ^[2]	0.43 ^[3]
Wood/Resin, 'pull-compression'	5 ^[1]	6.0 ^[3]	6.0 ^[3]	96.8 ^[3]	37.2 ^[3]	37.2 ^[3]	0.43 ^[3]

Sources: ^[1] nominal values as provided by the manufacturer; ^[2] experimentally derived values from Toumpanaki et al. (2022); ^[3] experimentally derived values from Toumpanaki et al. (2021); ^[4] $K_{nn} = 2.6 K_{tt}$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 5a and 5b show the pull-out load versus loaded end slip response for both the experimental and numerical findings and for the ‘pull-pull’ and ‘pull-compression’ test methods, respectively.

Figure 5: Pull-out load versus loaded end slip.

In the ‘pull-pull’ tests the use of the experimental stiffness, K_{tt} , results in a better fit between the experimental and numerical findings. In the ‘pull-compression’ tests a higher numerical stiffness equal to $10 K_{tt}$ results in a better agreement between the experimental and numerical results. The pull-out failure load and secant ultimate limit state stiffness of the numerical analysis at $10 K_{tt}$ are 4% and 8% higher than the respective experimental average values in the ‘pull-compression’ test. In the ‘pull-pull’ tests, the experimental pull-out load versus loaded end slip plots in Figure 5a were derived after cyclic loading at 15%, 30% and 45% of the ultimate failure load. Each cycle consisted of three load (tension)-unload-reload (compression)-unload repetitions. After completion of the cyclic loading regime, tensile loading to failure took place. Therefore, residual deformation due to the cyclic loading has already taken place and the reference point of recording the slip values resulted in greater axial and shear deformations and greater total loaded end slip values, as discussed in Toumpanaki et al. (2022). The experimental findings in Figure 5b refer to monotonic loading to failure and there is a restricting effect from the reaction frame that results in lower slip values. In all FE simulations regardless of the test method, the use of 100 times higher contact stiffness results in higher pull-out failure loads. The secant stiffness at the serviceability limit state (10-40% of the ultimate failure load) is similar between the FE simulations at $10 K_{tt}$ and $100 K_{tt}$.

Figure 6 shows the axial strain distribution, ϵ_{11} , in the glulam specimens at the vicinity of the glue-line for the specific numerical simulations that showed good agreement between the experimental and numerical findings. For ease of comparison, strain plots where the compressive strains are shown with black colour are also included in the figure. The strain data refers to the ultimate failure load of the numerical simulations.

Figure 6: Contours of direct strains, ϵ_{11} , from FE models at the numerical ultimate failure load.

In Figure 6a the ‘pull-pull’ test specimen is mostly under pure tension with the highest local strains taking place at the end of the bonded length. The tensile strains in the glulam specimen increase along the bonded length due to the bond stress transfer mechanism and the tension stiffening effect. Compressive strains develop at the edges of the specimen and close to the loaded end attributed to the lower elastic modulus of timber, higher compliance and Poisson’s ratio effects. In Figure 6b the ‘pull-compression’ test specimen is under compression with limited tension taking place at the edges of the specimen and at the centre close to the loaded end. In Figure 6b it is observed that some local compressive strain concentrations take place in the glulam specimen at the edge of the steel plate. At the vicinity of the steel plate, the compressive strain field with a magnitude of up to -1.4×10^{-4} extends up to 37 mm along the specimen.

Figure 7 shows the strain profiles, ϵ_{11} , in a typical ‘pul-pull’ and ‘pull-compression’ test as derived by DIC analyses. In both analyses the subset size was kept the same at 37 pixels with subset spacing of 1 pixel. The strain subset size was 100 and 51 pixels for the ‘pull-compression’ and the ‘pull-pull’ tests respectively. A good agreement is observed between the strain contours in the DIC and the FE analysis in the ‘pull-pull’ test specimen. The axial compressive strain field is greater towards the loaded end of the specimen in the DIC analysis. Greater axial strains are expected in the DIC analysis since the specimens were cut close to the bond line and the beneficial effect of the timber off-cut that enables greater strain distribution in the timber cross-section is neglected. Therefore, greater deformations are expected. In the ‘pull-compression’ test, the tensile strain field, ϵ_{11} , is extended to the end of the bonded length as opposed to the FE simulations. A better agreement is observed for the shear strains, ϵ_{12} , between the FE and DIC studies in the ‘pull-compression’ test, as shown in Figure 8. The high shear strains are more extensive in the DIC analysis but the general shear strain

contours are similar. Deviations between the DIC and FE analyses are expected due to the quality of speckle pattern, out of plane deformations and potential misalignment of the rod that causes local strain concentrations. Due to the lack of a non-linear material model and timber failure criterion in the FE simulations any material softening and strain re-distributions cannot be captured.

Figure 7: Contours of direct strains, ϵ_{11} , from the DIC analysis.

Figure 8: Contours of shear strains, ϵ_{12} , in the 'pull-compression' test.

Figures 9 and 10 show the longitudinal displacement plots for a 'pull-compression' and a 'pull-pull' test specimen accordingly, as derived by FE and DIC analyses. A good agreement in the displacement contours can also be observed between the FE and DIC analyses. The longitudinal displacements are more uniform along the bonded length in the 'pull-compression' test compared with the 'pull-pull' test where a parabolic displacement distribution is observed.

Figure 9: Longitudinal displacements (UT2=V) in the ‘pull-compression’ test methodology at failure.

Figure 10: Longitudinal displacements (UT2=V) in the ‘pull-pull’ test methodology at $P=20$ kN.

To compare the ‘pull-pull’ test method with the ‘pull-compression’ test method, two separate models were run with the exact same parameters, i.e., glue-line thickness of 3 mm and contact stiffness of $K_{tt}=15.4$ MPa mm. The aforementioned studies referred to different glue-line thicknesses to enable ease of comparison with the DIC test specimens. Figure 11 shows the pull-out load versus loaded end slip response for both test methods. According to the numerical simulations the failure load is 1.6% higher in the ‘pull-pull’ tests and there is no difference in overall stiffness at both the SLS and ULS between the test methods. Similar findings were derived from the GIROD project (Gustafsson & Serrano, 2002) where FE studies in glued-in steel rods suggested that the ‘pull-compression’ test method results in lower axial load capacities with increasing bonded length ($L_b > 50$ mm). It should be noted that in both the current and the GIROD FE study the wood material non-linearity was not modelled and the local material non-linearities in the bond test responses were simulated with the bilinear traction-separation cohesive law at the wood/resin contact interface where most failures lie.

Figure 11: Numerical pull-out load versus loaded end slip response for a typical ‘pull-compression’ and ‘pull-pull’ test.

CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this study is to compare two main bond test methods commonly employed for the characterisation of the withdrawal capacity of glued-in rods in timber and shed light on observed experimental failure load deviations via FE and DIC analyses. By assuming a bilinear traction-separation cohesive law (commonly used for epoxy adhesives) it is shown here that the initial cohesive stiffness can be modified to represent local material nonlinearities which would otherwise not be accounted for. Results suggest that when the numerical contact stiffness is up to ten times higher the experimental values, a good agreement between the experimental and numerical pull-out load versus slip response is attained for both test methods. The ‘pull-compression’ test method results in high local compressive axial strains at the vicinity of the steel reaction plate and high shear strains but no significant changes in failure loads were observed in the FE analyses between the ‘pull-compression’ and the ‘pull-pull’ test method. Limitations in current FE methodologies for glued-in rods in timber where wood material non-linearities and failure criteria are neglected should be considered. Displacement and strain fields from the FE model are shown to be in qualitative agreement with those obtained by DIC. A validation and design approach via FE and DIC analyses can provide a better insight in more accurate modelling of glued-in rods in timber and lead to more robust and efficient structural models where the joints are modelled as non-linear spring elements.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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